

Impact of Education on Human Development in Karnataka - An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

Globalization is unstoppable. The world is getting more connected through technology and travel. It has produced a new level of interdependence among us. A global competition has come into action. The whole world is being driven towards technology. Globalization is good. They say if trade stops, war starts. Somewhere between these connections all through the planet, a global peace exists. But major population of the planet is not even aware of globalization. It has become more like a one sided thing. Rich folks are getting richer and no impact on the poorer section of the society. Besides all that industrialization, growing population is disturbing the natural ecosystem. Pollution is on its run to take over the world. It is turning difficult to maintain a clean lifestyle with sustainable development. A major section of the society isn't aware of any of these situations. Alongside globalization, to attain a sustainable growth pace, new technical minds, fresh talents are needed. Majority of the population are illiterates, which suggests human resource development is certainly necessary. Human resource development helps citizens get better, get more technical about their work, family affairs and overall life. Educated minds can only survive this competitive era. Human resource development provides a stage for an all-round development of individuals. There are a number of indicators of human resource development. This paper aims in representing education as a way to human resource development. Considering the Indian education system, there are goods and bads, rights and wrongs. It is necessary to discuss the problems of the present education system and figure out reasonable, practically possible solutions. Education helps one carve a better society. Human resource development, aims at creating skillful minds, which in turn build a technically advanced society, attaining sustainable development. When people themselves can realize the importance of our ecosystem, they tend to not harm it anymore. So this paper is a try to discuss the relation between education and social welfare.

Keywords: Globalization, Sustainable growth, Social welfare.

Introduction

The world is getting more connected through technology and travel. Globalization is a worldwide movement towards economic, financial, trade and communications integration. Globalization has impacted nearly every aspect of modern life. Most economists agree that globalization provides a net benefit to individual economies around the world, by making markets more efficient, increasing competition, limiting military conflicts and spreading wealth more equally around the world. The sole Moto of this was to further enrich

and empower the society. But in the present scenario the rich and the powerful ones are getting enriched at the cost of the poorer and weaker causing environmental degradation, increasing poverty, unemployment, discrimination, inequality and injustice. The poor and the medium class families are still facing as much hardships as before. In the contemporary world, the word social welfare sounds more theoretical.

Social welfare defines the quality of a society. It isn't just the standard of living of the people. It gives a picture of how the whole system is operating. The government and non-government sectors, living status of population in the rural and urban areas, the environmental health, crime and drug abuse as well as the religious and spiritual aspects of life. One approach to attain a socially satisfying life style is by empowering every citizen with employment opportunity. Maintaining better health, keeping the environment healthy and attaining a overall better social life. With an economic perspective, for reaching a better financial state, require better upgraded minds. Human resource development is certainly necessary.

Many statistical investigations carried in western countries have shown that output increases at a much higher rate than can be explained by an increase in physical aspects like labour and physical capital. Human resource development encompasses development in several dimensions of human well-being. The reason is that the quality of human beings as a productive source has been consistently improving due to improvement in education and skills, availability of health services etc.

Methodology

The methodology of the present study relies on the secondary data and information of national and state level. "Human resource development, education and social welfare" is studied on the basic of available secondary sources such as government publications; Government Education Policy reports, various state and national journals and books.

Objectives of the Study

- The need for the human resource development.
- The indicators of human resources development.
- Role of the human resource development in the growth process and economic growth.
- Contribution of the education to the human resource development.
- Relation between education and social welfare.
- Relevance of the government education polices to development of human resources in the country.

The Need for Human Resource Development

In our common understanding we consider human resources and human beings as the same. But from an economic perspective, there is a difference between both. Human resource indicates those people with a high level of knowledge, ability, experience and willingness to perform a particular work, in general those who contributes economically to the country. The active human resource of a country plays an important role in economic development of that country. In fact effective use of physical capital itself is dependent upon human resource development. This is due to the reason that if there is underinvestment in human resources the rate at which additional physical capital can be productively utilized will be limited since technical, professional and administrative people are required to make effective use of material resource. Developing technical minds under various social and economic sectors could help create a better world. For an all-round development of a country there are a wide range of sectors from agriculture to science and technology. The approach below is to know the importance of human resource development in soul sectors of the society.

- **Agricultural development:** If per capita real income is low, emphasis is being laid on agriculture and other primary industries. An increase in agricultural production and the rise in the per-capita income of the rural community, leads to economic growth. Human capital directly proportionate to the agriculture development. More the efficient working groups, more is the agricultural output and so is the economic contribution. Appreciable human capital with strategic approach towards agriculture results to a better output. In the first place, due to lack of encouragement and appreciation with fair prices, most of the country's population is being driven towards urban areas, leaving agricultural practice. Along with that due to lack of basic education and strategic approach, the final yield is not reaching the expected qualitative cutoff. So this turns out to be the crucial time to educate these minds about the scientific approach to earn a better yield in agriculture. Apart from that if educated, farmers can't be cheated by any third party dealer in the market. So human resource development seem to be the best solution for the current scenario.
- **Development of industries:** In the present situation of globalization, the development of any country is accelerated by the establishment of industries. Currently India is a best country for startups. Using this situation, entrepreneurs must come up with new organizations small scale and large scale. The currently established organizations could make a better profit and progress by learning more about economy, finance, trade and banking facilities. Being industrially sound, keeps the country's economy high. So this needs huge human capital with skill, educated, sound technical knowledge and creative ideas.
- **Large scale production:** Human resource is one of the active factors of production. It is that factor which only uses other factors such as capital, land and organization for the production. To have more man power directly proportionate to the final output.
- **Sustainable development:** Organizing principle for meeting human development goals while at the same time sustaining the ability of natural systems to provide the natural resources and ecosystem services upon which the economy and society depend. The concept of sustainable development can be effectively implemented with the help of skilled and active human resources. Mobilization of skilled minds in different fields of production helps to achieve the faster economic growth and sustainable development.

The Indicators of Human Resource Development

Human resource development is not a physical capital. So it is hard to quantify and measure it like any other physical goods traded in the market. Yet we could consider a few terms and study the human resource development. Any activity that intensifies man's productive capacity adds in to the human resource development. The following are some of such activities,

- Health facilities and services, broadly conceived to include all the expenditure that affect the life expectancy, strength and stamina and the vigor and vitality of the people.
- Formal education at the elementary, secondary and higher levels. The last two are particularly important in indicating the stock of high-level man power.
- On-the-job training, including old-style apprenticeships organized by firms.
- Study programs for adults including extension programs specially in agriculture
- Migration of individuals and families to adjust changing job opportunities.

Education and Human Resource Development

Education shapes our present actions, our future plans and our past history which also develops in the future. Education is a crucial guide for the all-round development of an individual. It helps you to better understand the world and with that being said education plays a huge role in the

human resource development. So education and skill training boosts human resource development in the following ways:

- Education and economic growth: Education has been viewed as an important determinant of economic well-being. Various studies have been conducted by economists to assess the contribution of education in economic growth.
 1. It helps in creating a more effective skillful labour force.
 2. It helps in creating widespread employment and income-earning opportunities for workers under various sectors.
 3. It helps in creating a well-educated class of leaders to fill in the vacancies left by departing expertise or vacant positions in government and non-government organizations.
- Education and income inequalities: Education is believed to be a fine tool for the poorer population to overcome poverty and to create a normal proper life. Though it could not be concluded that education solves the problem of income inequality, education could upgrade the workers to a skillful level and hence help them earn a better pay scale. Moreover education makes people aware of the corruption and cheating happening around them.
- Education and rural development: Education can contribute to the rural development up to a significant level. By widening the horizons of knowledge of the rural people, it can help them overcome superstitions. The most important point is that, educating and introducing the farmers to new scientific strategies and techniques of agriculture for a much better yield qualitatively and quantitatively. Educating the villagers about self-employment, like small scale industries, swasahasangha and other banking and financial ways.
- Education and family planning: Education helps in modernizing and revolutionizing the ways of thinking of the people, making them aware of the scenario of a small family, happy family. It helps them realize their purpose of life, maintaining a small sophisticated family. It helps them to realize various health plans and programs launched by the government. Education widens their thinking. It helps to earn knowledge about health insurances, various beneficiary banking facilities etc.

Apart from all the benefits mentioned above, education helps young minds come up with new and creative ideas. It exposes an individual to a better social life. One can understand global affairs and be updated about the surrounding social environment.

Education Policies in India

Realizing the need for a change in the education system the government constituted an education commission under the chairmanship of Professor D.S Kothari. With the terms proposed by the commission, the government launched the National Education Policy in 1968. The following are some of the important features:

- All children up to the age of fourteen should get compulsory education. Elementary education was made free.
- To improve the standard of education the condition of teachers should be improved and particular attention should be given to their salary scale.
- To meet the requirements of agriculture and industry curriculums different levels should be modified.
- To bring uniformity in the character and standard of education in all the states a fifteen years education system should be introduced.
- For national integration, it was considered necessary to learn three languages. Hindi, English and one regional language around the country.

District Primary Education Program (DPEP), SarsvaShikshaAbhiyan (SSA)/ Right to Education (RTE), National Program For Education of Girls at Elementary Level (NPEGEL), Rastriya Madhyamil Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA) for development of secondary education, launched in 2009, Inclusive Education for the Disabled at Secondary Stages (IEDSS), Saakshar Bharath/ Adult Education, RashtriyaUchchatarShhikshaAbhiyan(RUSA) for development of higher education, launched in 2013 and National Policy on Education 2016.

Apart from Union Education Minister, all states are free to initiate more education policies. The Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE) is the highest advisory body to advise the central and state governments. In the year 2016 many new education policies have been introduced. Some of them are as follows.

- No detention policy to end for class 5 and 8. The Human Resource Ministry has decided to revise the old policy that promoted all the students from class 5 and 8. Now under the new policy, it will be mandatory for all students of class 5 and 8 to clear the examination so as to get into next class. As per the RTE (Right to Education) Act, on April 1, 2010, the policy was enforced with the motive of providing education to each and every child between the age of 6 and 14.
- No varsity can deny admission to student till final degree is issued. Delhi high court marked a decision that provisional certificate issued by a varsity works valid till a degree is issued, so no university can deny admission if a student cannot submit his previous degree.
- Students not allowed pursuing two regular degrees together.
- Free higher education for the poor. Assam government announced free higher secondary, three-year degree and polytechnic diploma courses for students who can't afford them.
- Education facilities for students with disabilities. The Guwahati government has announced a scheme of free education to disabled students from class 9 till the university level. It will include government-run institutions of higher education including professional colleges of engineering, medical and polytechnic.
- Government teachers to be sent to abroad for training. Delhi government announced that school teachers and principals would be sent to reputed foreign institutions to undergo training.
- Himachal Pradesh CM launched the Rajiv Gandhi Digital Student Yojna.

Problems of Indian Education System

1. According to Indian Human Development Report, despite considerable improvement in the literacy status, India is home to the largest number of illiterates. Having the drop outs number high, the illiterate number also is increasing. This is because children who do not complete a minimum of five years schooling are unlikely to retain literacy or numeracy skills in their adulthood.
2. In spite of all the effort made by the government, the quality of education in many rural area and certain urban places, is not appreciable. The teachers are not well trained. Many situations where teacher is absent or irregular to the schools have been encountered. The children are losing interest towards academics due to lack of creative teaching techniques. Today's education has turned into a rat race.
3. Lack of proper infrastructure has been a very serious problem yet not solved. The quality of Indian schools is abysmal. Especially in rural areas, the classrooms are not even having the basic infrastructure. Overcrowded classrooms, lack of teaching aid, dull teaching methods, all these drawbacks turn into discouragement to the children. Under these circumstances education has failed to make any significant improvement in the life of most of the rural population.

4. Private educational institutions have the worst fees regulation system. The fee structure is reaching so high that middle class society isn't being able to afford to study there. Many a times, education quality is also not much appreciable. Children are dragged into the race with a wring motive.
5. Reservation system favoring the poor and backward classes of the society is slowly turning into a social evil. Though it is helping the backward classes to reach a better lifestyle both socially and economically, it is affecting the other class of the society. Many talents miss the opportunity to have better educating platforms and get driven into something they are not much interested in. This is the biggest loss for the country.
6. The higher education system at present is so weak. Increase in number of substandard institutions, deterioration of academic standards, outdated curriculum, and failure to maintain academic calendar and lack of adequate support for research are some of the major drawbacks seen lately.

Suggestions for Improving the Education System

- Skill based learning: Schools should be allowed to provide skill based training. It can be done best by recognizing the areas of interest on any student. Skill based training might help in self-employment.
- Concentrate on Rural Education: It is believed that the future of India lies in villages. Knowing the significance of the rural areas, the government should provide practically helpful plans. It is necessary to appoint good teaching faculty, to provide a better creative infrastructure. The government should specially fund money for the development of rural education. It's equally important to monitor the fund being used properly without corruption.
- Providing technical training: In the present time of globalization, technology is getting more important than anything else. So it is necessary to provide the population, basic computer skill and introduce them to the latest technologies.
- Teachers training: It is necessary to create uniformity in teaching standards all over the country. Every levels of schooling, requires its own level of creative and skillful teaching. The teaching faculty should be trained in this way. The head authority of the respective education institutions must consider this seriously to recruit good teaching faculty, and should be constantly checked on about their performances.
- Financial support: The present day education has become a business. The scenario is like, the more money you pay, the better education you get. Private educating bodies have become nightmare to the common folks. The government must provide subsidies and other education loans favoring weaker sections of the society. Rules regulating the fee structure in private bodies should be brought into action immediately.
- Educating parents and guardians: Educating parents is equally important so that they do not force their children to for career which do not actually interest them. In rural areas, children have to be a part of family's income source. They will be put to work for daily labor. Government and non-government organizations should make an effort to awaken the illiterate minds. Making the families realize the power of education can make a big difference. The government must provide plans to financially support these families.
- Smart classes: To introduce smart class is a great move because along with improving infrastructure, it provides a technical vibe for the students. Many educational institutions have already adopted smart classes. But only the richer class is being able to afford this facility. Government should implement this method to every government schools and colleges.

- Educating girls: The parents have to widen their thinking about female education. It has been a wrong attitude of parents towards girl child. Government should strictly pass rules and laws to punish parents involved in act of not educating their girl child. Economic support should be provided and plans must be launched benefiting the female part of the society.

Conclusion

The function of education is to teach one to think intensively and to think critically. Intelligence plus character- that is the goal of true education. Education is the passport to the future, for tomorrow belongs to those who prepare for it today. With all the hurdles in the current education system, India is still making progress in a global level. Indians are employed all over the world. India is full of talented creative minds. They need a proper exposure. It is certainly possible with education. By taking a technical path to approach your line of work, it lets to gain better and higher outcomes. Applying this strategy in every sector of the society helps national economy grow. Agriculture, science, technology, space science, literature and commerce etc, all these fields having well trained minds can lead to economic growth of the country.

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